

Effect of Role Conflict in Teacher Trainers Job Satisfaction and Professional Commitment

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the impact of role conflict, professional commitment, and job satisfaction on teacher educators in Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh, India. In particular, the aim of this study was to find out the importance of the effect of role conflict on professional commitment and job satisfaction. This study used 100 teacher educators teaching B.Ed. Kanpur Colleges. A descriptive research questionnaire was used. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire. As a result, while role conflict had a significant effect on job satisfaction, both role conflict and job satisfaction did not have a significant effect on professional commitment. Indirectly, job satisfaction acts as a mediator between role conflict and professional engagement in B.Ed. colleges in Kanpur.

Keywords: Role Conflict, Job Satisfaction, Professional Commitment, Teacher Trainers.

INTRODUCTION

Teacher trainers are the pillar of the society that acts as a flame and shows the right path to become a responsible citizen of the country. Teacher trainers bring about multifaceted development and spiritual development of students, which shapes their personality. A person who wants to become a teacher must acquire the professional qualification of the teacher, creativity, good communication skills, communication skills and professional skills, be a learner himself and have the ability to deal with different learners. A teacher setting an ideal model before students can inspire them to discover their hidden talents and achieve their goals. The quality of teaching depends on the satisfaction of teacher trainers with their work. Thus, the field of job satisfaction needs due importance. We know that the teaching profession is one of the most important arts to guide students through different teaching methods, so it should attract the brightest minds, the best personalities and the most devoted young people to the profession. It requires people to be right. kind of attitude towards teaching will definitely be a successful teacher in the future. A professionally engaged teacher educator must have all the qualities of a professional teacher. As a profession, teaching was considered the noblest profession. A teacher has to play a different role to complete the task effectively, which sometimes causes different problems, such as stress, which leads to role conflict. Role conflict is basically a conflict between different expectations of a role. If two teacher trainers have different expectations of the other teachers' roles, role conflict is likely to occur. Role conflict arises from how we see each other every day and what role we give each other at work, in family life and in relationships. In educational settings, teacher trainers often suffer from role conflict, not only when they try to take on roles that society deems inappropriate, but also when they try to overcome their own biases and prejudices about what certain types of teacher trainers can or cannot do.

JOB SATISFACTION

It refers to motivation of employees for their work. It is a positive impulsive response that employees experience while at work. Simply put, job satisfaction is how good you feel at work. Job satisfaction as the positive affective reaction of an individual to the target environment, which results from the assessment of the individual of how much the environment satisfies his needs. Job satisfaction is very important to consider when it comes to employee self-fulfilment. Employees who do not get job satisfaction never reach psychological maturity and in turn become disillusioned. Job satisfaction is a suggestion of achieving fair compensation because it is very important for individuals and organizations to improve employee commitment to the organization. In this study, the job satisfaction of teacher trainers refers to the attitude of one teacher and work, which must be developed during school work to work with high morale, discipline, enthusiasm and commitment to the profession. Teacher trainers who are satisfied with their school can influence the smoothness of teaching and learning in the school and improve the quality of services provided to students.

PROFESSIONAL COMMITMENT

Professional commitment is a teacher's commitment to their profession, which is characterized by consistency, professional loyalty, professional competence and adherence to professional standards and ethical principles. The teaching profession requires commitment. An effective educator must be committed not only to their students, but also to their teaching profession as a whole. This means following the rules and regulations that cover the principles and requirements of the teaching profession. According to research, professional commitment is the attitude that someone has towards their work. This is their vision and active participation in the profession. A teacher's commitment helps separate those who are engaged in their profession and those who are not. Individuals who are dedicated not only to their students and their school, but lifelong learners who are dedicated to the teaching profession.

ROLE CONFLICT

All social structures, from a small unit like the family to a larger unit like the nation, consist of a complex structure of relational positions. These positions are actually classifications of people who share some similar characteristics and have certain design relationships with members of other positions. Certain positions set up by people are described, viz. a person takes a position quite independently of his desires or achievements. Role conflict concerns one of the most important features of social life and typical behaviour patterns. It explains roles by assuming that individuals are members of social positions and have expectations of their own and others' behaviour. Basically, role conflict is the situation of performing different tasks at the same time and under the same conditions.

TEACHER TRAINERS

A teacher is someone who helps other people acquire the knowledge, skills and attitudes they need to be effective teachers. The initial or continuing training of each teacher usually involves several individual teachers. Often, each of them specializes in teaching different teaching areas, such as educational ethics, educational philosophy, educational sociology, curriculum, pedagogy, subject-specific teaching methods. In some traditions, the term teacher-educator may be used instead of teacher-educator. Teacher trainers can be narrowly defined as professionals from higher education institutions, whose main activity is the preparation of novice teacher trainers both in universities and other institutions as well as in teaching

institutions, such as teacher training colleges. A broader definition could include any professional work that contributes in some way to the attainment of basic education. for training or continuing professional development of the school and other teachers. Teacher educators include staff involved in pre-service teacher education, educators who provide teacher training and development workshops and programs, online educators, and educators who provide in-service teacher training. Teacher trainers who supervise and supervise other teacher trainers or teacher trainees, material developers, educational researchers, managers and school leaders who are responsible for teacher training and development.

RESEARCH LITERATURE REVIEW

Indrani Sukul (2023) examines the job satisfaction of teaching staff in state-aided universities. He used descriptive type of research method using purposive sampling method. It selects 110 SACT teacher trainers from four general education colleges in North 24 Parganas district, West Bengal. The researcher develops a self-developed job satisfaction scale for SACT teacher trainers as a data collection tool. ANOVA and T-test are used to analyze the data. The result shows that the teaching staff of the government aided college of North 24 Parganas district is satisfied with their work to some extent. The main findings of this study are that various variables such as gender, age and teaching experience do not affect the job satisfaction of SACT teacher trainers in North 24 Parganas.

Shinde and Shah (2023) tried to identify various factors affecting the professional. dedication of high school teachers. The study is empirical in nature. Basic information is collected through a structured questionnaire. Systematic research is conducted on the target respondents of school teachers. The sample size remains 104. Kruskal-Wallis frequency distribution, descriptive statistics and non-parametric test were used in this context. It was found that there were no differences in professional commitment between high school teachers. Among high school teachers, there is great disagreement about their professional commitment. Almost all demographic profiles of teacher trainers (age, experience, professionalism, motivation, etc.) were observed to have significant P-values below 0.05. This means that there are no major disagreements except for the appointment of teachers. Teacher involvement is an asset in nation building tasks. This research will be useful to various stakeholders related to the world of education, which will increase the professionalism of teachers.

Su and Jiang (2023) described that work and family are the two most important parts of a person's life. Individuals cannot juggle their work demands and family responsibilities at the same time, so they face the dilemma of scheduling and role conflicts. Based on retention theory, this study investigated the relationship between work-family conflict and job satisfaction among 422 female university faculty members in China and proposed a moderating mediation model to examine the mediating role of burnout and the moderating role of perceived professional support. The results show that work-family conflict has a significant negative predictive effect on job satisfaction; burnout fully mediates the work-family relationship and job satisfaction; perceived professional support moderates the relationship between work-family conflict and burnout, and the stronger the perceived professional support, the weaker the negative predictive effect of work-family conflict on job satisfaction.

Prahlad Adhikari (2022) considers that job satisfaction refers to the positive feelings that an employee receives from various aspects of his work. Work stress is stress caused by work and work. Employment discrimination is the concept of unfair treatment in the workplace. Job satisfaction can protect against job stress caused by employment discrimination. A web-based questionnaire was developed in Google Forms to test the hypothesis that job satisfaction moderates the relationship between occupational discrimination

and job stress among Nepali workers. During the first three months of 2022, a snowball sample was taken from 278 employees working in different professions. A moderation analysis was performed and the results showed that high and medium but low job satisfaction protects against job stress due to occupational discrimination. A quarter of the employees were satisfied with their work. Job satisfaction was significantly negatively related to discrimination and job stress. The conclusion is that employers should try to increase employee job satisfaction in workplaces with more discrimination in order to protect employees from the negative consequences of job stress. Future studies focusing on specific occupations can be conducted to test the same hypothesis.

Pandey and Singh (2022) define that professional climate and professional commitment are the most important elements for the development and healthy process of any educational institution. The quality of the teaching work and the learning environment largely depends on the climate of the organization and the professional commitment of the teachers. In this study, the researcher wanted to find out the difference between professional climate and teachers' professional commitment. Therefore, 56 teacher educators from 5 B.Ed. colleges were selected for the study. Samstipur University and Begusrai District of Bihar. Professional Climate Inventory (Form B) developed by Som Nath Chattopadhyay and K.G. Agarwal (1976) and Professional Commitment Scale developed by Ravinder Kaur Ranu and Sarvjeet Kaur Brar (2011) were used for data collection. Levene's test and t-test were used to test the hypotheses. Main results: A significant mean difference was found in the professional climate dimension: performance standards of male and female teacher educators. No mean difference was found between male and female teacher educators in other dimensions of professional climate. It was also found that there was no significant mean difference in the professional commitment of male and female teacher educators.

Devi and Mantry (2022) described that role conflict occurs when a person tries to perform multiple tasks simultaneously and has difficulty completing them. This study investigated the level of role conflict among secondary school teacher trainers in Jammu municipality in terms of gender, academic orientation and teaching experience. This study used a descriptive survey method. Data was collected from 200 teacher trainers using convenience sampling method. Responses were collected using a standardized tool called "Teacher Role Conflict Scale" developed by Dr. Madhu Gupta and Indu Nain. T-test and one-way ANOVA was used to analyse the data. The most important finding of the study shows that there are differences in the role conflicts of secondary school teacher trainers in relation to their teaching experience.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of the study are as follows:

- To investigate the effects of role conflict on job satisfaction
- To investigate the effects of role conflicts on professional commitment
- To investigate the effects of job satisfaction on professional commitment
- To investigate the effects of role conflicts on professional commitment. the effect of role conflict on professional commitment through job satisfaction.

HYPOTHESIS TO BE TESTED

H1 : Role conflict has a significant negative effect on job satisfaction

H2 : Role conflict has a significant negative effect on professional commitment

H3 : Job satisfaction has a significant positive effect on professional commitment

H4 : Role conflict affects professional commitment through job satisfaction.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is a quantitative study using an explanatory and causal approach. The purpose of this study is to determine the causal relationships between the independent variables role conflict and professional commitment in Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh, India using job satisfaction influencing variables. The respondents used in this study were all teacher trainers who teach B.Ed. Kanpur Colleges up to 100 Teachers. The survey return rate in this study was very high among the respondents (100%), which was due to the fact that the researchers visited the study site every day during the distribution of the questionnaires. A total of 100 received questionnaires (87%) could be analyzed. Structural equation model analysis (SEM analysis) with Smart PLS is used in this study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Structural model testing is done to predict a causal relationship between variables or to test hypotheses, see significance value and R-squared research model. The purpose of testing a structural model is to predict the fit and also to see the magnitude of the structural path coefficients. The structure test model is performed in Smart PLS through a bootstrapping process. The R-squared value is used to calculate the Q-squared test of predictive validity, which measures how well the observed value is produced by the model as well as its parameter estimates. Q-square values greater than 0 indicate that the model has predictive importance, while Q-square values less than 0 indicate a model with lower predictive importance. The magnitude of the Q-squared value ranges from 0 to Q² and <1, where a Q-squared number approaching 1 means that the model is improving.

Square Dependent Variable

Dependent Variable	R Square
Job Satisfaction	0.127
Professional Commitment	0.104

Based on the table above, the Q-squared value is 0.031 or 3.1%. This Q Square value is the value of role conflict as an independent variable in this study, which gives an effect of 3.1% value on professional commitment through job satisfaction as an intermediate variable. This means that this research model has predictive significance because its value is greater than 0, so it can be declared useful in predictions. The results of this calculation also mean that 69% of the other variables can influence the commitment of an organization to B.Ed. College Teacher trainers in Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh, India. Exploratory Hypothesis Testing with Path Coefficient and T-Statistic Values. Path coefficient testing is a measure of the significance of hypothesis support that can be used to compare T-tables and T-statistic values. If the T-statistic value is greater than the T-table value, the hypothesis is supported. At the 95 percent confidence level (alpha 5%), the two-sided hypothesis T-table value is ≥ 1.64 . The results of structural model testing are shown in the table below:

Structural Model (Inner Model)

Inter Variable Relationships	Path Coefficient	T Statistic	P Values	Description
Effect of Role Conflict on Job Satisfaction	0.250	2.727	0.003	Significant

Effect on Role Conflict on Professional Commitment	0.037	0.230	0.403	Not Significant
Effect of Job Satisfaction on Professional Commitment	-0.108	0.950	0.171	Not Significant
Role Conflict influences Professional Commitment through Job Satisfaction	-0.027			Partial Mediation

The terms partial mediation and full mediation help convey the magnitude of the impact or practical importance of the mediation process. Full representation of mediation means that the underlying process can fully relate the independent variable to the dependent variable, while partial representation of mediation means a partial relationship.

Testing Hypothesis 1 : Role conflict's effects on job satisfaction. According to the study's final hypothesis, role conflict in Teacher trainers at Uttar Pradesh State Kanpur have a substantial detrimental impact on contentment at work. The examination outcomes on the parameter coefficient relating to how conflict affects employment .The value of satisfaction was positive, with a coefficient value of 0.250 and 2.727 for the T-statistic. The test's outcomes show that role conflict has a major beneficial impact on employment contentment.

Second hypothesis testing: Role conflict's impact on professional commitment .According to the theory that has been developed, there is a role conflict for teacher trainers in B.Ed. Colleges have a noteworthy drawback impact on the dedication of the organisation. The examination outcomes on the parameter correlation between professional and role conflict dedication demonstrates a favourable impact, with the coefficient value is 0.037, and 0.230 is the T-statistic value. indicating that the role conflict of instructors have a negligible beneficial impact.

The third hypothesis test examines how job satisfaction affects professional commitments. According to the third hypothesis, job satisfaction of Teacher trainers at B.Ed. Colleges are notably favourable for dedication inside the organisation. The parameter test results correlation between professional effectiveness and work satisfaction commitment point to a detrimental outcome suggested by a statistical T-value of 0.950 and a coefficient of -0.108. This indicates that teachers' job satisfaction does not significantly harm dedication inside the organisation.

Hypothesis Testing 4: How Role Conflict Affects Job Satisfaction and Professional Commitment .According to the theory, role conflict exists in Teacher trainers at Colleges in Kanpur have a major detrimental impact on employment happiness as a means of demonstrating professional commitment. The test of indirect influence magnitude yielded the results acquired by use of the path's coefficients (beta) relating role conflict's direct influence on job happiness and directly impacted by the job contentment with the organization's dedication to Teacher trainers at B.Ed. Colleges in Kanpur.

CONCLUSIONS

The results of the data analysis show that role conflict B.Ed. Colleges teacher trainers in Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh ,India have no significant positive effect on professional commitment, that is, if the teacher’s

role conflict is very high or low, the teacher remains committed to the organization where he works. Emotional exhaustion for teacher trainers in B.Ed. Colleges a significant positive effect on professional commitment because a teacher who is constantly exhausted while working can become committed to his or her organization. Role conflict in teacher trainers of B.Ed. Colleges in Kanpur has a significant positive effect on job satisfaction, which means that the less conflict a teacher has with his job, the greater his satisfaction. Emotional exhaustion teacher trainers has a significant negative effect on job satisfaction. Teacher has no significant negative effect on professional commitment, which means that if a person feels dissatisfied with his work, the teacher is not committed to his organization. Role conflicts do not affect professional commitment and job satisfaction acts as a mediating variable between role conflicts and professional commitment. This means that role conflict can significantly affect professional commitment in teacher trainers without working by changing job satisfaction. Professional commitment is affected by emotional exhaustion job satisfaction as a mediating variable of teachers, which means that emotional exhaustion can significantly affect the professional commitment of teacher trainers directly or indirectly through job performance. The practical implications of the findings of this study were addressed to especially the teacher trainers who wanted to increase teacher resources through programmed programs, clear division of labour, loads according to ability and motivation. For that implement a counselling and guidance system, are expected to minimize the number of teacher trainers experiencing role conflict and severe emotional exhaustion, although of these teacher trainers are satisfied and committed to the organization and should to stay maintaining a balance between tasks, workloads that are not redundant. The existence of this study can be used for pay attention to B.Ed. Colleges teacher trainers who experience role conflict and emotional exhaustion in their work.

REFERENCES

1. Sukul, I. (2023). *Job satisfaction of state Aided College teachers with respect to their gender, areas and teaching experiences in North 24 Parganas, West Bengal*
2. Shinde, M., Shah, A., & Patil, P. (2023). *Impact of various demographic factors on professional commitment amongst school teachers*
3. Su, Q., & Jiang, M. (2023). *The relationship between work family conflict and job satisfaction of female university teachers in China: A moderated mediating model*
4. Adhikari, P. (2022) . *Satisfaction as the moderator between discrimination and stress at work*
5. Pandey, S., & Singh, V. (2022) . *A study of Organizational climate and Professional Commitment of teacher educators*
6. Devi, S., Mantry, A., Lalotra, S., & Pradhan, B. (2022) . *Role conflict among government higher secondary schools teachers in Jammu & Kashmir*